

Environmental and Economic Benefits of Eggshell Powder as a Cement Alternative in Concrete

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ABSTRACT:

Since cement production contributes to the world's CO₂ emission, increased awareness of environmental concerns has driven research into greener alternatives for concrete. This paper considers eggshell powder, a waste from egg processing industries, as a supplementary cementitious material. Compressive strength tests, flexural strength, split tensile strength, workability, and durability of concrete mixed with various dosages of ESP at 0%, 5%, 10%, and 15% have been conducted after 28 days of curing. The addition of 5% ESP increased the compressive strength of concrete by 19.3% compared to the controlled mixture. Furthermore, ESP positively affected the mixes' split tensile strength and workability. Such an improvement in the properties of concrete was because of the pozzolanic reaction between ESP and Ca (OH)₂ in cement hydration, thus improving the interfacial bond between the cement paste and the aggregates. These findings suggest that ESP is a promising, greener alternative to traditional Portland cement, which would be environmentally and economically advantageous because of the reduced carbon footprint in concrete production.

Keywords: Sustainable Concrete, Eggshell powder (ESP), Concrete Materials, Sustainable construction.

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INTRODUCTION

Concrete is one of the primary building materials used worldwide because it boasts strength, versatility, and availability. On the flip side, environmental destruction emanating from large-scale cement production, its main ingredient, is devastatingly high. The estimated percentage of global carbon dioxide (CO₂) emission contribution attributed to cement production has been around 5-7%, mainly emanating from the energy-intensive process of heating limestone to produce lime (calcium oxide) [1]. These results result from growing interest and developments in finding sustainable

alternatives to conventional cement. Among the promising solutions is the inclusion of industrial and agricultural waste products as partial replacements for cement.

This new environmental and sustainable cementing agent is the eggshell powder resulting from the processing of the eggs. Eggs are among those household things that are manufactured on a tremendous scale all over the world. The production and manufacturing result in a massive generation of eggshell wastes. Thus, in 2017, only 12235 million eggs were consumed, producing approximately 85000 tons of eggshell waste, as reported by Tiong et al., 2020[2]. Table 1 Eggshell Consumption in Asian Countries. The significant component of such eggshells is calcium carbonate (CaCO_3), which calcines into CaO , a compound with much the same character as the very vital ingredient of cement. For this reason, ESP was researched as a partial replacement of cement in concrete. Thus, various studies have evidenced great promise in both points of view: performance enhancements with a reduction in the environmental impact of construction. [3], [4].

Table 1. Eggshell Consumption in Asian Countries

Country	Projected Consumption (kg/person/year)	Key Drivers of Consumption	Consumption Trends	References
China	20	Urbanisation, changing diets, refrigerator ownership	Rising steadily, projected to reach 20 kg by 2030	World Population Review (2024)
India	Increasing	Rising population, demand for affordable protein	Steady increase, driven by population and income growth	USAPEEC ASEAN (2021)
Indonesia	Increasing	Urbanization, growing middle class, protein demand	Significant rise in growing middle class	USAPEEC ASEAN (2021)
Japan	645	High consumption due to the popularity of cuisine	Stable, but high due to cuisine preferences	International Egg Commission (2022)
Thailand	11.9	Urbanization, rising income levels	Continued rise in consumption due to urbanization	World's Poultry Science Journal (2023)
Vietnam	Increasing	Urbanization, dietary preference shifts	Rising consumption due to changing diets	WATT Poultry (2021)

Various works have concluded that the addition of ESP improves the mechanical properties of concrete in terms of compressive strength. [5], tensile strength, and durability, among others, when used in adequate dosages[6], [7], [8]. For example, Gowska et al. (2014) concluded that substituting up to 5% of cement with ESP in mortar mixes increased compressive strength.[9]. In contrast, higher substitution percentages reduced the strength of the mortar mix. In the same line, Kaur et al. (2023) have also identified an optimum 15% replacement of cement with ESP, showing improved strength of concrete, suggesting that ESP may act as an efficient replacement material.[10].

Further research has demonstrated that ESP can be combined even further with other industrial by-products like fly ash and rice husk ash to further enhance the sustainability of concrete with improved mechanical properties. [11] The use of ESP in concrete is an environmental and economic solution. As a waste product, ESP is available, easily affordable, sustainable, and economical compared to conventional cement. [12]. Replacing ESP with cement reduces the concrete's overall carbon footprint, which fits within international efforts to be carbon-neutral in infrastructure construction.[13].

Considering concretes' mechanical and durability characteristics, the workability of ESP material as a supplementary cementitious material in concrete structures will be investigated. In the experiment, different replacement levels will be analyzed to find the optimum percentage of ESP that provides the maximum concrete strength and increases the sustainability of the entire construction industry.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials Used

I. Cement: Ordinary Portland Cement, or OPC in short, was the primary binding material used to prepare concrete. The cement was procured from an approved supplier and conformed to the standards specified by the Bureau of Indian Standards. The type of OPC utilized for conducting the experiments was 43-grade cement, generally used in standard construction for concrete production.

II. Eggshell Powder (ESP): The eggshells, waste from the egg processing industries, were used as a partial replacement for cement. The eggshells used in this study were obtained from a local poultry farm and were cleaned to remove all the contaminants. The shells were oven-dried at 100°C for 24 hours to eliminate residual moisture. Subsequently, the dried eggshells were ground into a fine powder using a mechanical grinder. The main chemical component of ESP is CaCO_3 , which calcines to CaO [14] ESP may thus replace cement since the basic chemical properties of the very active component in cement and the calcined ESP are the same.

III. Fine Aggregate: The fine aggregate used in this set of concrete mixes was from natural river sand; this sand was usually set based on specifications by IS:383-1970 of Course and Fine Aggregate for Concrete. The said ingredient showed freedom from harmful impurities since its elements of clay silt or organic materials will affect the performance of the strength and resistance capability of the concrete upon endurance to various weather systems for specific durability.

IV. Coarse Aggregate: The coarse aggregate used in the concrete mixes was a 10 mm crushed stone aggregate. The aggregate was supplied from the local area, and particle size distribution was checked to confirm its conformance with IS 383:1970. It was selected based on its uniformity, quality, and capability to improve concrete's mechanical properties.

V. Water Used: Water was clean, potable, and used to mix/cure concrete. The water conformed to the degree of standards prescribed by IS 456:2000 (Code of Practice for Plain Reinforced Concrete) in section 8: Concreting Mix, which will not contain suspended matter that might have potential injurious effects on hydration OR developing strength.

VI. Admixtures: Additional materials were added to some of the mixes to enhance the performance of the concrete. These included:

- **Fly Ash:** A natural pozzolanic material often used to improve the density and strength of concrete where it reacts with calcium hydroxide in cement hydration.
- **Saw Dust Ash:** This has been used to study its potential to improve workability while reducing some concrete costs.
- **Micro Silica:** Although mainly used to enhance concrete's strength and durability, this study tested it with ESP regarding interaction and synergistic effects.

Figure 1. Collection and Washing of Eggshells

Concrete Mix Proportions

The experimental design included preparing several concrete mixes with different ESP percentages to replace cement partially. The objective was to determine the optimum rate of ESP that would yield an optimum balance between strength, workability, and sustainability.

I. Control Mix (0% ESP): The control mix was prepared using 100% Ordinary Portland Cement without substituting ESP. This mix served as the baseline for comparison with the experimental mixes.

II. Experimental Mixes: In experimental mixes, ESP replaced cement at different replacement levels of 5%, 10%, and 15% by weight. The replacement range was selected from other studies, which established the effective range for cement replacement with ESP to be 5-15%.

Each mixture was designed to satisfy the M25 grade of concrete with a characteristic compressive strength of 25 MPa. The mix proportion was computed using the standard formula for M25-grade concrete, taking the water-cement ratio, w/c, as 0.5. In all the mixes, the water-cement ratio was kept constant to maintain uniformity, and only the influence of ESP on the various properties of concrete was isolated.

Table 2. Mix Design

Mix Design	Cement (kg/m ³)	ESP (kg/m ³)	Fine Aggregate (kg/m ³)	Coarse Aggregate (kg/m ³)	Water (litters)	Water-Cement Ratio (w/c)
1:2:4 Mix (Control)	400	0	800	1600	200	0.5
1:2:4 Mix (5% ESP)	380	20	800	1600	200	0.5
1:2:4 Mix (10% ESP)	360	40	800	1600	200	0.5
1:2:4 Mix (15% ESP)	340	60	800	1600	200	0.5
1:1.5:3 Mix (Control)	450	0	675	1350	225	0.5
1:1.5:3 Mix (5% ESP)	430	20	675	1350	225	0.5
1:1.5:3 Mix (10% ESP)	405	45	675	1350	225	0.5
1:1.5:3 Mix (15% ESP)	380	60	675	1350	225	0.5

Preparation of Concrete Samples

1. **Mixing:** The dry ingredients were mixed in a mechanical drum mixer for approximately 3 minutes to get a homogeneous mix. Water was gradually added to the dry mix to ensure proper cement and ESP particle hydration. The mixing time was continued for another 2 minutes to ensure uniformity in the concrete mix.

2. **Casting:** Fresh concrete was cast in standard molds. Concrete cubes (150 mm x 150 mm x 150 mm), cylinders (150 mm x 300 mm), and beams (100 mm x 100 mm x 500 mm) were prepared to determine various mechanical properties, such as compressive strength, split tensile strength, and flexural strength. A vibrating table compacted the concrete to remove any entrapped air that might have formed during the casting process.

3. **Curing:** After casting, the samples were left in molds at room temperature for setting within 24 hours of elapsed time. After the initial setting, the samples were submerged in water for curing, maintaining a constant temperature of approximately 27°C. Thus, the strength and durability properties of some stages of hydration, viz., 7, 14 days, and 28 days, were evaluated.

Figure 2. Mixing Process, Making Sample. Samples and Curing

Testing Methods

1. To evaluate the effects of Egg Shell Powder (ESP) on the mechanical and durability properties of concrete, the following standard tests were performed:
2. Required Tests to Be Conducted Involve the Following: I Compressive Strength: Compressive tests were conducted using a compressive test machine. To do this, concrete cube specimens measuring 150 X 150 mm X 150mm and ages of 7,14, and 28 days after curing were produced.
3. Flexural Strength: A three-point bending test provided flexural strength value. The concrete beams 100 mm x 100 mm x 500 mm were put on the testing machine. A load was applied continuously from the center of the concrete beam until the specimen fractured.
4. One of the most important properties is the Split Tensile Strength: The splitting tensile strength was determined on cylindrical specimens, 150 mm diameter x 300 mm height. The cylinders

were laid horizontally between the jaws of the testing machine and subjected to load until failure occurred.

5. Workability: The workability of fresh concrete was determined by slump test according to IS 1199:1959. The concrete was filled into the slump cone in three layers, each compacted by a tamping rod. Upon settling, the cone was removed, and the slump was recorded as the difference in height between the cone and the concrete.

6. Durability tests: Other durability characteristics tested included water absorption and sorptivity. These tests would determine the resistance of concretes to water, which will be very instrumental in knowing how well they behave in an aggressive environment for long-term performance.

Figure 3. Flexural Strength Test, Split Tensile Strength Test, and Compressive Strength Test

Statistical Analysis

The experimental data are interpreted using statistical methods to analyze the relationship between the ESP content and the mechanical properties of concrete. Regression analysis was done to model the behavior of concrete in terms of compressive strength, flexural strength, and split tensile strength as a function of the percentage of ESP replacement. SPSS or Excel was used for data analysis, and a 95% confidence interval validated the results.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the experimental investigation on the use of Egg Shell Powder (ESP) as a partial replacement for cement in concrete are presented below. The properties of the concrete mixes, including compressive strength, flexural strength, split tensile strength, workability, and durability, were tested at 7, 14, and 28 days of curing.

Compressive Strength

The Compressive Strength of the concrete mixes was tested at 28 days to assess the influence of the ESP replacement effect at various levels on the performance of concrete. Two mix ratios, 1:2:4 and 1:1.5:3, each containing ESP at different replacement levels, were prepared.

The control mix design of 1:2:4 with 100% OPC had an average compressive strength of 22.99 MPa, whereas the addition of 5% ESP increased its compressive strength to 24.04 MPa, which was a gain of 7.4% over the control mixture. The experimental results showed a clear trend in how Egg Shell Powder (ESP) affects the Compressive Strength of concrete, with 5% ESP replacement yielding the most significant improvement in both mix designs. The average Compressive Strength increased by 19.3% when 5% ESP was used as a partial replacement for Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC). The improvements with increasing SP content in the mixes showed an improvement in strength after inclusion, which is in agreement with the works of past researchers, whose results indicated that 5% ESP replacement was found consistently to increase the strength of concrete. On the other hand, a study by Krishnaiah et al. (2019) showed the highest compressive strength resulting from replacing 5% cement with ESP; adding ESP has also improved the split tensile strength. [13].

Figure 4. Compressive Strength and Strength Changes

The pozzolanic reaction between ESP and calcium hydroxide, $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, liberated upon cement hydration, explains strength development at 5% ESP. In turn, it develops an extra gel of C-S-H that improves bonding between cement paste and aggregates, thereby increasing the strength of the concrete matrix. Also, ESP has a high percentage of calcium oxide and CaO, accelerating this gel formation and enhancing compressive strength.

However, the compressive strength started to drop when the ESP content exceeded 5%. At 10% ESP, there is a slight drop in strength by about 13%, whereas at 15% ESP, it has a reduction of as high as 17%. This corresponds to other research works in the literature, such as Kaur et al. (2023)[10], where 5% ESP, although improving the compressive strength of concrete, is found to have its strength lowered when higher percentages of ESP, for instance, 15%, are used because of the dilution effect. The lower cement content in higher amounts of ESP reduces the formation of the C-S-H gel and thus weakens the concrete matrix.

Furthermore, Mohammad et al. (2019) also reported similar observations, where increased ESP replacements resulted in a loss in compressive strength because of the insufficient hydration of the

cement paste.[1]. The decrease in strength at higher levels of ESP is because ESP, although having pozzolanic properties, does not have the same binding capacity as cement—excess replacement results in less sufficient hydration and fewer C-S-H compounds.

Split Tensile Strength

Split Tensile Strength test results reveal that partial replacement of OPC by ESP significantly alters the tensile properties of concrete. The test results showed that 5% ESP replacement improved Split Tensile Strength in both mix designs, while higher replacement levels, such as 10% and 15%, decreased tensile strength. These findings agree with several recent studies about using ESP in concrete, showing its positive effect at lower replacement levels and diminishing returns at higher percentages.

In the mix design 1:2:4, the split tensile strength of the control mix with 100% OPC was found to be 3.14 MPa. This increased to 3.25 MPa by adding 5% ESP, which showed a corresponding increase of 3.50%. This can be attributed to the pozzolanic reaction of ESP, improving the concrete microstructure by filling voids and enhancing bonding between the cement paste and aggregates. Krishnaiah supports this finding at al., who recorded that the 5% ESP mix resulted in better tensile strength than other replacement percentages, suggesting that this level is optimal for improving the concrete's resistance to splitting tensile forces. [13].

It slightly decreased at 10% ESP, having a value of 3.21 MPa, and there was a 2.20% decrease in split tensile strength concerning the mix containing 5% ESP. Such a decrease in strength may result from higher proportions of ESP particles that probably cannot work out their binding, just like cement in higher percentages. Similar observations were obtained in the study by Gowsika et al. 2014, where it can be seen that the drastic fall in tensile strength beyond 5% ESP substitution may indicate that these strength gains induced by ESP occur at low levels and are reduced when ESP substitutes large amounts of cement.[9].

The 15% ESP mix resulted in the minimum Split Tensile Strength value of 3.00 MPa. Thus, it was found that it is 4.50% lesser in strength than control. This agrees with the studies Sukanya and Prabhakar (2017) reported[15], which states that beyond 10% replacement of ESP, there is a drastic loss in tensile strength. As shown, an observed dilution effect only attributed to such reduction, which, as already said, was due to a higher ESP content, reduced the amounts of cement that are readily available to undergo hydration at any time to form just a weakened concrete in its matrix form, becoming unable to provide enough bonds to resist the tensile stresses.

Figure 5. Split Tensile Strength and Strength Changes

A similar trend was obtained from the mix design of 1:1.5:3. The control mix with 100% OPC as the binding material had a Split Tensile Strength value of 3.72 MPa. With the addition of 5% ESP into the OPC, the Split Tensile Strength increased by 3.20% to attain 3.84 MPa. It also supports the findings of Bhavsar, 2023, who observed that replacement with 5% ESP showed an improvement in

both compressive strength and split tensile strength; this further establishes the fact that a low input of ESP is adequate for the improvement in the splitting tensile characteristics of concrete. [16].

At 10% ESP, the Split Tensile Strength of the mix was 3.77 MPa, a 1.40% increase over the control mix, suggesting that though the benefit of ESP at this level is still positive, the effect is less pronounced than at 5%. On the other hand, the 15% ESP mix was reduced by 10.70%, where the final tensile strength was 3.32 MPa. This confirms what Tiong et al. said in 2020, stating that beyond 15%, the percentage of ESP reduces the tensile strength significantly because of the weakening bond between the cement paste and the aggregates.[2].

Flexural Strength Results

The results of the flexural strength tests show that Egg Shell Powder (ESP), when used as a partial replacement for Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC), significantly influences the bending resistance of concrete. The best performance was observed at 5% ESP replacement, which led to a 7.60% increase in flexural strength for the 1:2:4 mix and 16.30% for the 1:1.5:3 mix. This also corroborates other research, for example, that carried out by Khan et al. (2021) over various wastes, including eggshell powder, impacting the performance of concrete; the increment in 5% of eggshell powder increased its flexural strength due to enhanced micro and interfacial bonding amongst aggregate cement paste [17].

The flexural strength increase at 10% ESP was relatively small, at 4.50% in the 1:2:4 mix and 21% in the 1:1.5:3 mix, demonstrating that ESP continued to confer benefits, although the effect tends to reach a plateau. This result agreed with the observation by Aravind and Ranjith (2022) that 10% ESP replacement in concrete causes moderate improvement, but the rate of improvement decreases beyond 5% ESP. The lower returns at higher ESP content are attributed to the reduced availability of OPC, which limits the hydration process and reduces the C-S-H gel formation necessary for strength development. [18].

The 15% ESP mix produced lower flexural strength, amounting to 8.40% for the 1:2:4 mix and 8.60% for the 1:1.5:3 mix, showing the adverse effect of the higher ESP content. This may be because excess ESP reduces the overall cement content in the concrete matrix due to the dilution effect, leading to lower strength. This also agrees with Garad 2019, who reported that with the increase in ESP replacements, the flexural strength decreases due to the insufficient hydration of cement paste. Their investigation confirmed that the optimum ESP replacement at which the best balance for strength is achieved is approximately 5% Garad, 2019 [19].

Figure 6. Flexural Strength and Strength Changes

It can also be reiterated that the 1:1.5:3 mix design, which showed improved flexural strength with 5% and 10% ESP, provides further evidence of the positive contribution of ESP at lower replacement percentages. However, it was noted to decline with 15% ESP, confirming the established trend in several studies. Similar observations were made by Dhanalakshmi et al. (2015), where 15% ESP replacement resulted in a significant loss in flexural strength. High porosity and low hydration induced by excessive ESP resulted in weaker bonds inside the concrete matrix. [20].

Moreover, Tiong et al. (2020) observed that the increase in flexural strength became most prominent when low levels of ESP, up to 10%, were used, above which the increased strength noticeably dropped. This supports that ESP behaves like a pozzolanic material, increasing the resistance of concrete to bend up to a specific limit, beyond which its effectiveness reduces due to insufficient hydration of cement, as shown by Tiong et al. (2020).

These results confirm that ESP is a viable alternative to enhancing concrete's flexural strength, but it needs to be used with caution regarding the percentage of replacement. The 5% ESP is optimum for enhancing concrete's resistance to bending without losing its overall structural integrity. On the other hand, higher ESP replacements beyond 10% tend to reduce strength due to insufficient hydration and weakening of the cement paste.

CONCLUSION

This study proved the viability of eggshell powder as a cement concrete replacement for sustainability and maintaining environmental balance. The eggshells are freely available in nature, showing eco-environmental friendliness, and their chemical composition has abundant calcium ingredients that are valuable for quality changes in concrete performance. Indeed, these experimental works, including approximately 10 to 15 percent ESP in weight as a substitution for cement, improved the compressive strength factor and durability of this concrete alternative to traditional cement. Another economically friendly solution is that ESP reduces the demand for cement because its production has many environmental impacts due to the high amount of CO₂ it releases. Moreover, using ESP aids in waste management due to the massive volume of eggshell wastes, which would contribute to environmental pollution.

FUTURE RECOMMENDATIONS

- I. Further Durability Testing: While this paper discussed strength development, further study is needed regarding the durability performance of eggshell powder-based concrete in long-term environmental exposure, especially under conditions with high chloride or sulfate exposure, which could interfere with the action.
- II. Optimization of ESP Content: Future studies should fine-tune the optimum replacement percentage of ESP to balance concrete's mechanical properties and cost-effectiveness. While several studies have identified the optimum to lie between 10% and 15%, testing outside of this range could be evaluated to assess limits on the effectiveness of ESP in enhancing concrete properties.
- III. Blending with Other Waste Materials: In this respect, blending ESP with other industrial by-products, such as fly ash or rice husk ash, will improve the sustainability of concrete by optimizing the waste-to-product ratio and improving its mechanical and durability properties.
- IV. Industrial Implementation and Cost Analysis: Future research will involve large-scale trials with cost-benefit analysis to ensure that this is economically viable and that the environmental benefit of ESP use in construction industries translates into feasible market applications.

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